

Scripts

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#####  
# Appendix Sx. linear mixed-effects model (LMM)  
#####  
# This script fits linear mixed-effects model to  
# analyse the effects of predictors (x1-x10) on the response  
# variable 'ig'.  
#  
# x1-x8 : continuous predictors  
# x9    : interaction term  
# x10   : categorical factor (reference level = "CMd")  
#  
# Random effect: intercept for grouping variable PLOT  
# Estimation method: Maximum Likelihood (REML = FALSE)  
# Multicollinearity assessed using VIF  
# Model performance metrics calculated  
#####  
  
## Required packages  
library(lmerTest)  
library(performance)  
library(car)  
library(openxlsx)  
library(tibble)  
  
## Ensure categorical variable is properly defined  
data$x10 <- factor(data$x10)  
data$x10 <- relevel(data$x10, ref = "CMd")  
  
## Fit global mixed-effects model  
model_global <- lmer(  
  ig ~ x1 + x2 + x3 + x4 + x5 +  
      x6 + x7 + x8 + x9 + x10 +  
      (1 | PLOT),  
  weights = weight,  
  REML = FALSE,  
  data = data  
)  
  
## Model summary  
summary(model_global)  
  
## Multicollinearity diagnostics  
check_collinearity(model_global)  
vif_values <- vif(model_global)  
  
## Model performance metrics  
model_performance <- performance(model_global, metrics = "all")  
  
## Export results  
coef_table <- as.data.frame(coefficients(summary(model_global)))  
coef_table <- rownames_to_column(coef_table, "Variable")  
write.xlsx(coef_table, "global_model_estimates.xlsx")
```

```
write.xlsx(as.data.frame(model_performance),
           "global_model_fit_statistics.xlsx")
```

```
vif_table <- as.data.frame(vif_values)
vif_table <- rownames_to_column(vif_table, "Variable")
write.xlsx(vif_table, "global_model_vif.xlsx")
```

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```
# Appendix Sx. Marginal predictions from the global LMM
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```
# This script generates marginal predictions from the
# global mixed-effects model (model_global).
```

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#
```

```
# For each predictor (x1-x9), predictions are calculated
# across its observed range while holding all other
# predictors at their mean values.
```

```
#
```

```
# Predictions are computed without random effects
# (population-level predictions; re.form = NA).
# Results are exported to an Excel workbook.
```

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```
## Required packages
```

```
library(lme4)
```

```
library(openxlsx)
```

```
## -----
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```
## 1. Compute mean values of predictors
```

```
## -----
```

```
mean_values <- list(
```

```
  x1 = mean(data$x1, na.rm = TRUE),
```

```
  x2 = mean(data$x2, na.rm = TRUE),
```

```
  x3 = mean(data$x3, na.rm = TRUE),
```

```
  x4 = mean(data$x4, na.rm = TRUE),
```

```
  x5 = mean(data$x5, na.rm = TRUE),
```

```
  x6 = mean(data$x6, na.rm = TRUE),
```

```
  x7 = mean(data$x7, na.rm = TRUE),
```

```
  x8 = mean(data$x8, na.rm = TRUE),
```

```
  x9 = mean(data$x9, na.rm = TRUE),
```

```
  x10 = names(sort(table(data$x10), decreasing = TRUE))[1] # most frequent category
```

```
)
```

```
## -----
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```
## 2. Prediction function
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## -----
```

```
generate_predictions <- function(var_name, var_range, mean_vals, model) {
```

```
  pred_data <- data.frame(
```

```
    x1 = mean_vals$x1,
```

```
    x2 = mean_vals$x2,
```

```
    x3 = mean_vals$x3,
```

```
    x4 = mean_vals$x4,
```

```
    x5 = mean_vals$x5,
```

```

    x6 = mean_vals$x6,
    x7 = mean_vals$x7,
    x8 = mean_vals$x8,
    x9 = mean_vals$x9,
    x10 = factor(mean_vals$x10, levels = levels(data$x10))
  )

  pred_data <- pred_data[rep(1, length(var_range)), ]
  pred_data[[var_name]] <- var_range

  predictions <- predict(model, newdata = pred_data, re.form = NA)

  data.frame(
    Variable = var_name,
    Value = var_range,
    Prediction = predictions
  )
}

## -----
## 3. Define predictor ranges
## -----

var_ranges <- list(
  x1 = seq(min(data$x1, na.rm = TRUE), max(data$x1, na.rm = TRUE), length.out = 50),
  x2 = seq(min(data$x2, na.rm = TRUE), max(data$x2, na.rm = TRUE), length.out = 50),
  x3 = seq(min(data$x3, na.rm = TRUE), max(data$x3, na.rm = TRUE), length.out = 50),
  x4 = seq(min(data$x4, na.rm = TRUE), max(data$x4, na.rm = TRUE), length.out = 50),
  x5 = seq(min(data$x5, na.rm = TRUE), max(data$x5, na.rm = TRUE), length.out = 50),
  x6 = seq(min(data$x6, na.rm = TRUE), max(data$x6, na.rm = TRUE), length.out = 50),
  x7 = seq(min(data$x7, na.rm = TRUE), max(data$x7, na.rm = TRUE), length.out = 50),
  x8 = seq(min(data$x8, na.rm = TRUE), max(data$x8, na.rm = TRUE), length.out = 50),
  x9 = seq(min(data$x9, na.rm = TRUE), max(data$x9, na.rm = TRUE), length.out = 50)
)

## -----
## 4. Generate predictions
## -----

all_predictions <- list()

for (var_name in names(var_ranges)) {
  all_predictions[[var_name]] <- generate_predictions(
    var_name,
    var_ranges[[var_name]],
    mean_values,
    model_global
  )
}

## -----
## 5. Export results to Excel
## -----

wb <- createWorkbook()

```

```

for (var_name in names(all_predictions)) {
  addWorksheet(wb, var_name)
  writeData(wb, var_name, all_predictions[[var_name]])
}

addWorksheet(wb, "Mean_values")
mean_df <- data.frame(
  Variable = names(mean_values),
  Mean     = unlist(mean_values)
)
writeData(wb, "Mean_values", mean_df)

saveWorkbook(wb, "global_model_predictions.xlsx", overwrite = TRUE)

## Combined dataset (optional)
combined_predictions <- do.call(rbind, all_predictions)
write.xlsx(combined_predictions,
           "global_model_predictions_combined.xlsx")

```

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#####
# Appendix Sx. Post hoc pairwise comparisons (Tukey test)
#####
# This script computes estimated marginal means (EMMs)
# for the categorical predictor x10 and performs
# pairwise comparisons using Tukey adjustment.
#
# Model: model_global
# Factor analysed: x10
#####

## Required package
library(emmeans)
library(openxlsx)

## -----
## 1. Estimated marginal means for x10
## -----

emm_x10 <- emmeans(model_global, ~ x10)

## -----
## 2. Pairwise comparisons (Tukey-adjusted)
## -----

pairwise_results <- pairs(emm_x10, adjust = "tukey")

## -----
## 3. Summary of results
## -----

summary(pairwise_results)

## -----
## 4. Convert results to data frame
## -----

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```
results_df <- as.data.frame(pairwise_results)

## -----
## 5. Extract statistically significant comparisons (p < 0.05)
## -----

significant_pairs <- results_df[results_df$p.value < 0.05, ]

## -----
## 6. Export results
## -----

write.xlsx(results_df, "posthoc_pairwise_comparisons.xlsx")
write.xlsx(significant_pairs, "posthoc_significant_comparisons.xlsx")
```